

This archive contains data files from the simulations of the Global Airglow model (GLOW) .

- The conductivity output files with different inputs are calculated from the GLOW model, which contain the ionization rate, electron density, and conductivity at the PFISR location.

These simulations were performed for and used in the paper “Ionospheric modulation by EMIC wave driven proton precipitation: observations and simulations” Xingbin Tian, Yiqun Yu, Fan Gong, Longxing Ma, Jinbin Cao, Stanley C. Solomon, P. R. Shreedevi, Kazuo Shiokawa, Yuichi Otsuka, Shin-ichiro Oyama, Yoshizumi Miyoshi, submitted to JGR, 2022.